

HIGH-STRAIN-RATE SUPERPLASTICITY OF SiC_p/8090 ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Superplastic tensile tests of a 17 vol.% SiC_p/8090 Al-Li composite were carried out at strain rates ranging from $7.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S}^{-1}$ to $3.46 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ and at temperatures from 773 K to 873 K. A maximum elongation of 300% was obtained at a strain rate of $1.83 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ when tested at a temperature of 848 K which was slightly above the solidus temperature of the composite. The effect of a small fraction of liquid phase on high-strain-rate superplasticity was discussed. Finally, based on the values of strain rate sensitivity m at two strain rate regions and the activation energy, high-strain-rate superplastic mechanism and low-strain-rate deformation mechanism were discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum based metal matrix composites (MMCs) are making inroads into the aerospace and automobile industries. However, in many cases, the characteristics of low ductility and poor formability of most MMCs are still causing concerns, and an improvement on ductility is obviously desired for many structural applications.

One of the methods of achieving high ductility in MMCs is to make them superplastic. Recent studies have indicated that certain discontinuously reinforced aluminum MMCs can behave superplastically. The findings of Nieh *et al* revealed that a 20 vol.% SiC_w/2124 aluminium composite produced by powder metallurgy behaved superplastically at a high strain rate of $3.3 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ [1]. Besides, a mechanically alloyed aluminium IN9021 alloy containing about 5 vol.% of very fine oxide and carbide particles also exhibited superplastic behaviour at a high strain rate of 1.3 S^{-1} [2]. Following these findings, some other MMCs produced by either the techniques of powder metallurgy [3-6] or mechanical alloying [7-9] were found to behave superplastically at high strain rates over 10^{-2} S^{-1} . In particular, a Si₃N_{4p}-6061 aluminum composite exhibited a large elongation of 620% at a very high strain rate of 2 S^{-1} [5], more still a Si₃N_{4p}-2124 aluminium composite had demonstrated a large elongation of 830% at a strain rate of $4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S}^{-1}$ [6]. These results are highly important since one of the major concerns of current superplastic forming technology is its slow forming rate, typically ranging from 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} S^{-1} . Thus, the discovery of high-strain-rate superplasticity in these MMCs has presented a major breakthrough in superplastic forming technology.

Among the many Al-based MMCs, SiC particulate reinforced Al-Li based composites possess many distinguishing properties such as lightweight and high stiffness. However, so far their superplastic properties are less investigated. With this in mind, this study aims to examine the superplastic behavior of an Al-Li alloy 8090 reinforced with 17 vol.% SiC particles.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND PROCEDURES

The composite material used in this study was a commercially available Al-Li based alloy (8090) reinforced with 17 vol.% SiC particles which have an average size of about $3 \mu\text{m}$. The matrix has a nominal composition of $AL-2.3Li-1.2Cu-0.7Mg-0.1Zr$ (wt.%). The MMC material was manufactured by powder metallurgy, and the material was supplied in sheet form having a thickness of 2 mm . A typical microstructure of the material is shown in Figure 1. In general, a uniform distribution of SiC particles was observed throughout the matrix, and also no void or crack was observed at interfaces between the SiC particle and the aluminum matrix.

Tensile specimens with a cross section of $4 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$ and a gauge length of 5 mm were machined from the sheet in such a way that the test direction was parallel to the rolling direction. Superplastic tests under temperatures from 773 K to 873 K were conducted in a three-zone split furnace with three independent proportional temperature controllers. Prior to testing, the specimen was held in the furnace at the specified test temperature for 15 minutes to establish thermal equilibrium and all the testings were conducted in air. The initial strain rates produced by different constant cross-head velocities ranged from 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} S^{-1} . The flow stress obtained for each true strain rate was determined at a fixed true strain of 0.2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effects of testing temperature and initial strain rate on the characteristics of true stress-true strain curves are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively. These two figures show that in all cases strain hardening was practically operated almost up to the point of failure and relatively little strain softening had occurred, except at the test temperature of 873 K at which an almost steady-state flow was observed. Apparently, the curves of the same initial strain rate show a larger elongation at the temperature of 848 K which was slightly higher than the solidus temperature. The effect of true strain on true stress at the temperature of 848 K and at strain rates from 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} S^{-1} is shown in Figure 4. Moreover, this figure also shows that an optimum superplastic strain rate was reached at a strain rate of $1.83 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ and at 848 K . In this case, the curve shows a relatively longer strain softening region.

The relationship between total elongation-to-failure and the initial strain rate at different test temperatures are shown in Figure 5. In general relatively low elongations were obtained at low strain rates. A maximum elongation of 300% was obtained at the strain rate of $1.83 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ at 848 K . Beyond this strain rate, the total elongations decreased. The optimum strain rates at which maximum elongation was acquired, increased from 10^{-2} to $1.83 \times 10^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ as the test temperatures increased from 773 K to 848 K . The total elongations, however, were lower at the temperature of 873 K which was 40 K higher than the solidus temperature.

As the solidus temperature of the composite is at about 833 K , local melting is likely to occur at the particle/matrix interfaces and grain boundaries of the matrix at temperatures above 833 K . Should this happen, the existing liquid film would act as lubricant as well as high diffusivity paths to promote sliding at particle/matrix interfaces and grain boundaries [10]. Nieh *et al* had

proposed that the presence of a liquid phase in materials was a prerequisite for MMCs to behave superplastically, and a rheological model was proposed to explain high-strain-rate superplasticity in MMCs [11]. However, the model shows its usefulness only when the volume fraction of liquid in MMCs is very high so much so that matrix grains and reinforcements are completely separated from each other. But, in fact in many cases, the fraction of liquid could not be too high since superplastic behaviour of MMCs was normally found at temperatures close to or just slightly above the solidus temperature of the composite. In these cases solid "bridges" would exist between particles. It is believed that the test condition at temperature of 848 K matches this picture. Thus, the existence of a small fraction of liquid phase in the form of thin lubricating films enhanced the tensile elongation-to-failure of the MMC at the temperature of 848 K. It was interest to note that a large elongation was not obtained when the test temperature was much higher than solidus temperature as happened at 873 K. This has led to the conclusion that a large volume of liquid phase present in the MMC material would not contribute to large elongations.

Examples of the fractured specimens deformed at various strain rates and at different testing temperatures were shown in Figure 6. It should be noted by comparison with the untested specimen that the superplastic specimens exhibit relatively uniform deformation with little or no necking. The fractured surfaces of the tensile specimens tested at 848 K and 873 K and at the strain rate of $9.9 \times 10^{-3} S^{-1}$ were shown in Figure 7 and 8 respectively. In the former case, the composites appeared to have fractured primarily in the matrix as a result of coalescence of cavities. Whereas, at temperatures much higher than the solidus temperature, as happened in Figure 8, some SiC particles were exposed on the fracture surface and it seemed to that the fracture was initiated at the matrix/particle interfaces.

Variations of flow stress with the instantaneous strain rate for testing temperatures from 773 K to 848 K were shown in Figure 9. The strain rate sensitivity, m , defined by the slope of the curve of $\ln \sigma \sim \ln \dot{\epsilon}$ at a true strain of 0.2 were also shown in Figure 9. The results show that the flow stresses at all test temperatures increased with strain rates. A transition in strain rate sensitivity was observed at a strain rate of about $10^2 S^{-1}$. In the low strain-rate regime which was below $10^2 S^{-1}$, the strain rate sensitivity of less than 0.1 was obtained which was an indicative of an apparent thermal threshold stress. In the high strain rate range between $10^2 S^{-1}$ to $10^1 S^{-1}$, a relatively high m value of $0.37 \sim 0.53$ was found.

Grain boundary sliding is generally believed to be the dominant deformation mode in fine-grain superplastic alloys [12]. In case of grain boundary sliding, the grain size is certainly the most important microstructural parameter. However, in discontinuous reinforced aluminum MMCs, in addition to grain boundary sliding, extensive interfacial sliding had been taken place. Although, a theoretical model for the prediction of interfacial sliding rate has not yet been developed, it would be similar to that obtained for grain boundary sliding [13]. The relatively high value of m found in this work should indicate that grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding could be the primary high-strain-rate superplastic deformation mechanisms operated in particulate reinforced MMCs at test temperatures slightly above the solidus temperature.

To explore the deformation mechanism of the composite at different strain rates and at temperatures slightly above the solidus temperature, the following constitutive equation was proposed by authors [14]:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \frac{D b \sigma^n}{k T G} \quad (1)$$

where, $A = \frac{(p-1)(2p-1)}{18.75\sqrt{3}[f(p-1)+p(2p-1)]}$ is a dimensionless structural parameter;

$f = [4\pi\sqrt{2/3}V_r]^{1/4}$ is the volume factor;

V_r is the volume fraction of the reinforcements;

p is the ratio of the matrix grain size to the particle size of the reinforcement;

\mathbf{b} is Burgers vector;

k is Boltzmann's constant;

G is the shear modulus;

n is the stress exponent ($=1/m$) [15] and

D is the appropriate diffusion coefficient [$=D_0\exp(-Q/RT)$, where D_0 is a frequency factor,

Q is the activation energy for the diffusion process, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature].

Based on equation (1), the constitutive equations at temperatures slightly above the solidus temperature of the composite are derived as follow:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_1 = \mathbf{A}bD_0\exp(-Q_l/RT)\sigma_1^{n_1}/(kTG) \text{ at low strain rates;}$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_2 = \mathbf{A}bD_0\exp(-Q_h/RT)\sigma_2^{n_2}/(kTG) \text{ at high strain rates.}$$

where Q_l is the activation energy for deformation at *low strain rates* and Q_h is the activation energy for *high-strain-rate* superplastic deformation.

By combining these two equations, Q_l can be represented by the following equation,

$$Q_l = Q_h + RTLn\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_2 \sigma_1^{n_1}}{\dot{\epsilon}_1 \sigma_2^{n_2}}\right) \quad (2)$$

From Figure 9, the strain rate sensitivity for low strain rate and high strain rate were found to be about 0.1 and 0.5 respectively, also the stress exponent for two cases were determined to be 10 and 2 respectively. Furthermore, the activation energy for deformation at high strain rates was assumed to be equal to the activation energy for grain boundary diffusion (*i.e.* $=86.04 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [14]. By substituting these data and values of stresses and strain rates at two distinct regions at 848 K into equation (2), the activation energy required at low strain rate deformation was found to be $134.89 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ which was in fact close to the activation energy of lattice diffusion in aluminum ($=142 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). It is, therefore, believed that the controlling deformation mechanism in $\text{SiC}_p/8090$ Al-Li composite at low strain rate condition at temperatures slightly above the solidus temperature was considered to be related to lattice diffusion in the aluminum matrix.

SUMMARY

High-strain-rate superplasticity of a 17 vol.% $\text{SiC}_p/8090$ aluminum-lithium composite was investigated. A maximum elongation of 300% was obtained at a high strain rate of $1.83 \times 10^1 \text{ S}^{-1}$ and at a temperature of 848 K, which is slightly above the solidus temperature of the composite. This suggests that the existence of a small fraction of liquid phase was essential for the superplastic deformation to occur in the MMC. The exponent of strain rate sensitivity obtained at high strain rates indicated that grain boundary sliding and interfacial sliding would be the primary superplastic deformation mechanisms operated in the MMC when deformed at temperatures slightly above the solidus temperature of the composite. The value of the estimated activation energy indicated that the deformation mechanism at slow strain rates may be related to the lattice diffusion in aluminum matrix.

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Fig.1 A typical microstructure of the 17 vol.% SiC_p/8090 Al composite.

Fig.2 The effect of temperature on true stress vs true strain curve at the initial strain rate of $2.93 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}^{-1}$.

Fig.3 The effect of temperature on true stress vs true strain curve at the initial strain rate of $9.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}^{-1}$.

Fig.4 The effect of strain rates on true stress vs true strain curve at the temperature of 848 K.

Fig.5 Elongation vs initial strain rate curve for different test temperatures.

Fig.6 Examples of the fractured specimens at different conditions.

Fig.7 Fracture surface of a specimen tested at the strain rate of $9.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}^{-1}$ and at 848 K.

Fig.8 Fracture surface of a specimen tested at the strain rate of $9.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S}^{-1}$ and at 873K.

Fig.9 The changes of flow stress with true strain rate for 17 vol.% $\text{SiC}_p/8090 \text{ Al-Li}$ composite.